

UNPACKING PUPILS' READING ABILITY THROUGH PARENT-GUIDED READING INTERVENTION

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to determine the pupils' reading ability through parent-guided reading intervention. Specifically, this study tried to evaluate the pre-reading test scores of pupils of Pedro P. Santos Memorial Elementary and the post-reading test scores of pupils when parent-guided reading intervention was introduced. This research used a true experimental research design and employed a pre and post-reading test before and after the parent-guided reading instruction was used. The respondents of the study are 25 pupils who were tagged as nonreaders before the conduct of school-based reading tests. Mean gain score and t-test statistical tools used in processing the data. On the pre-reading test pupils before the conduct of parent-guided instruction were found to be in a Frustration Level which means pupils cannot read word/words without the assistance of the teacher. On the post-reading, after the parent-guided instruction was employed were found to be at a Frustration Level which means pupils cannot read word/words without the assistance of the teacher. Interestingly it was found that there is a big difference between the means of the pre-reading and post-reading scores of the pupils which implies that there's an improvement in the reading skills of the pupils.

Keywords: *Keywords: Pupils' Reading Ability, Parent Guided, Reading Intervention, Philippines*

INTRODUCTION

The shortcomings in basic reading abilities are known to have constrained millions of children from taking advantage of the extensive benefits of education. These include achieving high levels of fluency, learning more advanced skills, and progressing to higher levels of education in India according to Abadzi, H. (2012)

Reading is a distinct, cognitive human skill that is crucial to life in present societies, but, for about 250 million primary school-aged children in developing countries, learning to read was extremely difficult. Over half of all pupils in second grade cannot read a single word and almost 30 percent of all third-grade learners were zero-word readers Education for All.

Numerous DepEd initiatives purposed to develop and strengthen Filipino children's capacity to read in the early grades. These include the "Every Child A Reader Program (ECARP)," "project D.E.A.R (Drop Everything and Read)," "Reading Assistance Program," "Summer Reading Camp," the observance of "National Reading Month" every November, and other school-based reading activities. However, a report on the country's 2014 Early Grade Reading Assessment (EGRA) revealed alarming results. In letter-sound identification, 10- 25 percent of the pupils tested could not identify a single letter-sound correctly. Thus, this study draws on the implementation parent guided reading intervention among nonreader pupils of Pedro P. Santos Memorial Elementary School, President Quirino North District, Division of Sultan Kudarat

Research Questions

Generally, this study determines the unpacking pupils' reading ability through parent-guided reading intervention in Pedro P. Santos Memorial Elementary School.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the pre-reading test score of pupils of Pedro P. Santos Memorial Elementary School?
2. What was the post-reading test score of pupils of Pedro P. Santos Memorial Elementary School when parent-guided reading intervention was introduced?
3. Is there a significant difference in the pre-reading test score and post-reading test score of pupils after parent-guided reading intervention was introduced?

METHODOLOGY

This research used a true experimental research design and employed a pre and post-reading test before and after the parent-guided reading instruction was used. The respondents of the study are 25 pupils who were tagged as nonreaders before the

conduct of school-based reading tests. Mean gain score and t-test statistical tools used in processing the data.

RESULTS

On the pre-reading test pupils before the conduct of parent-guided instruction were found to be in a Frustration Level which means pupils cannot read word/words without the assistance of the teacher.

On the post-reading, after the parent-guided instruction was employed were found to be at a Frustration Level which means pupils cannot read word/words without the assistance of the teacher.

Interestingly it was found that there is a big difference between the means of the pre-reading and post-reading scores of the pupils which implies that there's an improvement in the reading skills of the pupils.

DISCUSSION

On pre-reading test scores of pupils of Pedro P. Santos Memorial Elementary School

De Dios (2013) emphasized that two of every five pupils in grade 3 who encountered difficulties in reading were likely to fail upon entering junior high school

Table 1. Level of Pre-reading Scores of Pupils

	Mean	Std Deviation	Description
Pre-Reading Test	38.65	13.73	Frustration Level

Table 1 shows the level of pre-reading scores of the pupils of Pedro P. Santos Memorial Elementary School. It has a mean of 38.65 which falls under "Frustration Level". This implies that the pupils have very poor reading skills. Maybe it is because the pupils were not yet exposed to some intervention.

The poor performance of the learners in reading competencies as portrayed in their below-average level in the pre-test can be associated with their failure to embrace the basic competence of decoding letter symbols and associating their names and as well as their corresponding sounds. This situation came up despite the clarity of the instructional medium which is the mother tongue of the learners. Somehow, in the given time provided to the learners, they have difficulty recalling appropriately each letter's name. Noticeably, only the first five letters in the alphabetical sequence are commonly recalled correctly.

On the post-reading test score of pupils of Pedro P. Santos Memorial Elementary School when parent-guided reading intervention was introduced

Table 2. The Level of Post-reading Scores of Pupils

	Mean	Std Deviation	Description
Post-Reading Test	82.19	11.05	Frustration Level

Table 2 reveals the level of post-reading scores of the pupils of Pedro P. Santos Memorial Elementary School after the parent-guided reading intervention was introduced. It has a mean of 82.19 which signifies that there is a big improvement in the reading skills of the pupils after the intervention has been introduced. This implies that the intervention was effective. However, it still falls under the “Frustration Level” which means that there is still a need to improve the reading skills of the pupils. This may also suggest that the intervention being introduced should be continued or other interventions should be employed.

On the significant difference in the pre-reading test score and post-reading test score of pupils after parent-guided reading intervention was introduced

Table 3. The Pre-reading and Post-reading Scores of Pupils

Reading Scores	Mean	p-value	Interpretation
Pre-reading Scores	38.65	.000	Significant
Post-reading Scores	82.1923		

Table 3 shows the difference between the pre-reading and post-reading scores of the pupils of Pedro P. Santos Memorial Elementary School. It can be gleaned that there is a big difference between the means of the pre-reading and post-reading scores of the pupils which implies that there’s an improvement in the reading skills of the pupils. Further, Table 3 reveals that the p-value is less than 0.05 level of significance which means the null hypothesis must be rejected. This further implies that the alternative hypothesis must be accepted. Therefore, it is safe to conclude that there is a significant difference between the pre-reading and post-reading scores of the pupils.

The findings correspond with Mwangi's (2018) study which found a strong relationship between both parents’ involvement in children’s reading at home and their performance in Kiswahili reading comprehension.

Likewise, Lumapenet & Andoy (2017) study revealed that parents’ assistance in reading significantly influences the oral and silent reading abilities of the children and that their parental self–motivation and empathy were found to be the best predictors of pupils’ reading abilities. Thus, the parents should enhance and strengthen their role in the education of their children.

Conclusions

The following conclusions are drawn based on the findings of the study.

The pre-reading test and post-reading test results are at a frustrating level. Meanwhile, though it was frustration level after employing the parent-guided reading instruction it was found out that there is a significant difference.

Recommendations

From the salient findings of this study and the conclusion reached, the following recommendations are presented. The school may continue its parent-guided reading instruction to eradicate nonreaders in school. The teachers may sustain their school's best practices in teaching reading. The teachers and school heads may continue or strengthen the parent engagement in the reading performance and academic performance of learners. This study be replicated in wide scope to have a clearer picture of parent-guided instruction and add variables not included in this study.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This paper has a single author and confirms the ethical standards.

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REFERENCES

- Abadzi, H. (2012). *Efficient learning for the poor: Insights from the frontier of cognitive neuroscience*. Washington, DC: World Bank.
- De Dios, A.C. (2013). *Philippine Basic Education*. Retrieved July 25, 2018 from: <https://www.philippinesbasiceducation.us/2013/01/every-child-reader-by-grade-1.html>
- Lumapenet, H. & Andoy, N. (2017). *Influence of the Family on the Pupils' Reading Performance*. 7th CEBU International Conference on Civil, Agricultural, Biological and Environmental Sciences (CABES-17) Sept. 21-22, 2017 Cebu (Philippines)
- Mwangi, J. (2018). *Parental Involvement in Reading: Does involvement translate to Performance in Kiswahili comprehension among elementary pupils in Kenya?* *International Journal of Scientific and Education Research* Vol. 2, No. 02; 2018